

This archive contains software, scripts and configuration files, input files and snapshots extracted from the trajectories for the paper” *Subtype selective mechanism of negative allosteric modulators binding to the group I metabotropic glutamate receptors*”.

“Software”:

- 1) In this work, molecular docking was performed based on Maestro. v. 9.0, which can be obtain from <https://www.schrodinger.com/Maestro>.
- 2) Gaussian 09 suite (version D.01) <http://gaussian.com/products/> was used to implement the geometric optimization and the electrostatic potential calculation of ligands.
- 3) All MD simulations were carried out with GPU-accelerated NAMD (version 2.12) <https://www.ks.uiuc.edu/Development/Download/download.cgi?PackageName=NAME>
- 4) All of the MD trajectories analyses were performed by using CPPTRAJ program of AMBER14 <http://ambermd.org/>.
- 5) PyMol (version 1.3) <https://pymol.org/2/#download> was used to visualize the structural features in this study
- 6) IChem (Version 5.2.8) <http://bioinfo-pharma.u-strasbg.fr/labwebsite/download.html> was utilize to Implement molecular interaction fingerprint analysis

“Scripts and configuration files”:

All MD simulation configuration files and main scripts needed for the work were shared in this file in the supporting information. Unzipping this file will create a directory containing the configuration files and scripts for the 100ns MD simulations and trajectories analysis.

“Input files”:

Input files including coordinates, topologies and parameter files used to MD simulation of the six NAMs-complexes.

“Snapshots extracted from the MD trajectories”:

The 500 snapshots extracted from the last 50 ns MD simulation trajectory of each NAM-complex in this study were provided, which are used to calculate the binding free energy analysis, computational alanine scanning and molecular interaction fingerprint analysis.

“Results”:

The data of per-residue decomposed energy, molecular interaction fingerprint, RMSD

values and the monitored angle of residue W798 or W785 in this study were shared.

If other additional information is necessary, please contact with Prof. Feng Zhu (zhufeng@zju.edu.cn) or Prof. Weiwei Xue (xueww@cqu.edu.cn).